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ANALYTICAL REPORT

”Release Without Freedom: Forced Expulsion of Political Prisoners and Legal Vacuum in the Republic of Belarus”

Limits of the Applicability of Humanitarian and Human Rights Guarantees under the Persistence of a Repressive Regime

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Executive Summary

This report analyses the formation in 2025 of a specific repressive mechanism in the Republic of Belarus, within the framework of which political prisoners are removed from places of deprivation of liberty without any legal completion of their criminal status and are subsequently forcibly expelled beyond the borders of the country. The report shows that this practice does not constitute release in the legal sense, but represents a special form of coercion based on the deliberate preservation of legal uncertainty.

The report establishes that persons subjected to this mechanism are released without annulment of convictions, termination of criminal proceedings, rehabilitation, or any formal determination of their legal status after leaving places of deprivation of liberty. As a result, they remain persons with an unfinished criminal status imposed by the state. Although physically they are outside places of deprivation of liberty and beyond the territory of the Republic of Belarus, they continue to bear the legal consequences of previously applied repressive measures in the form of an unclosed criminal position.

Based on documented cases, the report demonstrates that forced expulsion is not a collateral consequence of release, but constitutes its functional objective. Release is used as a technical stage of a broader procedure aimed at removing politically inconvenient individuals from the country. In practice, this mechanism is implemented through threats of renewed deprivation of liberty, pressure to leave, deprivation or non-issuance of documents, as well as organised escort to state borders under the control of law enforcement bodies.

The report identifies three consecutive waves of application of this mechanism in 2025, affecting a total of approximately two hundred individuals. Despite differences in scale, all waves possess identical legal characteristics, indicating a reproducible and coordinated practice rather than isolated decisions. In none of the documented cases was release accompanied by restoration of civil or political rights or by any legal act terminating criminal liability.

Special attention is devoted to the case of Nikolai Statkevich, which became the first publicly documented instance of refusal to comply with imposed expulsion. This case revealed the internal logic of the mechanism: refusal to leave the country is not regarded as a permissible option and entails renewed deprivation of liberty. Following this episode, the practice acquired stable and predictable features and was extended to subsequent groups of political prisoners.

From the perspective of international law, the described practice affects fundamental guarantees, including the right to legal certainty, the prohibition of arbitrary expulsion, and the right to return to one's own country. The report reaches the principal conclusion that within the existing international legal and institutional architecture there are no instruments capable of forcibly terminating the functioning of this mechanism inside the Republic of Belarus.

Under these conditions, international structures possess neither the right nor the factual ability to intervene in the internal decision-making framework, including even basic forms of negotiating influence. Their role is objectively limited to the recording and documentation of violations, their legal qualification, and the formation of an external international position. However, these instruments do not provide direct protection and are incapable of stopping the application of the repressive mechanism within the jurisdiction of the regime. As a result, the practice continues to be reproduced, and its consequences are systematically transferred beyond the territory of the Republic of Belarus and shifted onto host states and international structures.

Introduction

The Republic of Belarus has been under the rule of an authoritarian regime led by Alexander Lukashenko for more than thirty years. International organizations and states have repeatedly documented the absence of free and fair elections, the systematic suppression of political opposition, and the use of repression as an instrument of state governance. The results of the 2020 presidential election have not been recognized by a significant part of the international community, and the human rights situation in the country is assessed as severe and systemic.

Beginning in 2025, a mechanism was implemented and subsequently reproduced in the Republic of Belarus whereby political prisoners are not released in the legal sense. They are removed from places of deprivation of liberty and forcibly removed beyond the borders of the country within the framework of foreign political arrangements.

At the time of preparation of this report, three successive waves of application of this mechanism have been documented. The first wave (21 June 2025) included the release and subsequent forced removal of 14 persons from the country. The second wave (11 September 2025) covered an organized group of 52 political prisoners extracted from places of deprivation of liberty and expelled beyond the borders of the Republic of Belarus without legal completion of their status. The third wave (13 December 2025) acquired a mass character and affected 123 persons, in respect of whom similar violations were recorded: absence of termination of criminal prosecution, confiscation or non-issuance of documents, and forced removal beyond the borders of the country. All three waves represent stages of the same mechanism, differing in scale but not in their legal nature.

These actions are not accompanied by the termination of criminal prosecution or the restoration of basic civil and procedural rights. This mechanism in fact represents the use of political prisoners as an objects of foreign policy bargaining - the physical removal of people from the system of imprisonment followed by exile in exchange for sanctions-related or political concessions, rather than an act of humanitarian release. A key feature of these cases is that a person's exit from prison is not accompanied by the legal completion of criminal proceedings. In the majority of documented episodes, the following are absent:

- termination of the criminal case;
- annulment or review of the sentence;
- expungement of a criminal record;
- rehabilitation;
- an official procedural decision determining the legal status of the person after release.

As a result, a legal vacuum is created in which a person is formally outside places of deprivation of liberty but in fact remains fully dependent on the repressive apparatus of the state. This vacuum is used as a tool of pressure and control, whereby freedom is replaced by forced exile. Released individuals are subjected to the following:

- they are threatened with repeated detention;
- they are forced to leave the territory of the country;
- their documents are confiscated or not issued;
- they are transported to the state border under the control of security forces;
- they are effectively deprived of the possibility of return.

The report demonstrates that in the cases under consideration, forced expulsion is not a consequence of release, but its primary objective. Release is used as a technical stage of an operation aimed at removing politically inconvenient individuals from the country.

Within the framework of the present report, a principled distinction is made between the levels of subjectivity, roles, and responsibility of the parties involved in the process of the release and subsequent expulsion of political prisoners from the Republic of Belarus. The regime of the Republic of Belarus is considered the sole initiator, organizer, and direct executor of the repressive practice of forced expulsion. It is the state authorities of the Republic of Belarus that formulate, apply, and reproduce the mechanism of release without legal termination of status, using legal uncertainty and coercion to leave the country as instruments of internal and external control.

Legal responsibility for these actions and their consequences lies fully with the Belarusian state. The United States of America is considered a key external negotiating actor, which played a leading role in establishing and maintaining contacts with the Belarusian authorities and possessed the greatest capacity to influence the parameters and conditions of the releases. At the same time, the report records that after the first wave of releases, the United States did not put forward mandatory and publicly formalized conditions aimed at eliminating the identified defects of the mechanism, including the absence of legal termination of the status of released persons and the coercive nature of their departure. Such inaction does not constitute legal complicity; however, it has significant relevance for the assessment of political and institutional responsibility for the reproduction of this practice.

The European Union is considered a supporting and secondary actor, participating in the political and diplomatic framework of the release process, but not acting as a leading initiator of negotiations and not shaping the parameters of the practical implementation of the mechanism. The participation of the European Union was of a political and diplomatic accompanying nature, with limited capacity to influence the conditions of the releases and without independent instruments to compel the regime to correct the identified violations.

This differentiation is used exclusively for analytical purposes and is aimed at a correct assessment of the institutional role and political responsibility of external actors. It does not substitute the legal responsibility of the state that initiated the repression and does not equate diplomatic participation or negotiating mediation with complicity in human rights violations.

This practice performs several functions simultaneously:

- cleansing of the internal political space;
- creation of an external image of softening repression;
- use of human freedom as an instrument of pressure and bargaining within the context of sanctions policy.

A special place in the report is devoted to the case of Nikolai Statkevich, which became the first publicly documented example of refusal to accept imposed exile. This case made it possible to expose the essence of the mechanism: release does not imply the restoration of rights, and refusal to leave the country leads to an artificial legal status, intensified pressure, and complete legal uncertainty. It was precisely after this episode that the practice acquired systematic features and was extended to subsequent groups of political prisoners.

The report combines two interrelated analytical levels:

- documentation of factual violations, including forced transportation to the border, deprivation of documents, threats, and humanitarian risks;
- analysis of the mechanism through which the absence of legal completion of status is used as a form of continuation of repression already outside prison.

From the perspective of international law, the described practice affects fundamental guarantees: the right to freedom of movement, the prohibition of arbitrary expulsion, the right to return to one's own country, the right to legal certainty, and protection against arbitrary interference by the state. Where indicators of mass character and systematic nature are present, such actions may be considered a form of forced population transfer carried out as part of state policy.

The report concludes that existing international responses to these developments are predominantly declarative in nature and are not accompanied by the creation of practical mechanisms to protect persons subjected to expulsion. The absence of such mechanisms leads to the fact that the repressive policy of the state effectively continues beyond its territory, shifting the consequences onto host countries and international structures. In the concluding part of the executive summary, practical recommendations are formulated, addressed to international organizations and states, aimed at:

- ending the practice of expulsion under the guise of release;
- ensuring mandatory legal completion of the status of released persons;

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- protecting individuals who refuse to leave the country;
 - developing procedures for the reception and legalization of persons expelled without documents.
- This report examines not only the factual and legal aspects of this practice, but also the limits of applicability of existing humanitarian and human rights mechanisms under conditions of the continued existence of a repressive regime.

1. Terms and Conceptual Framework of the Report

This report uses strictly defined terminology. This is necessary in order to prevent the substitution of concepts, the dilution of responsibility, and the artificial shifting of emphasis from the substance of what is occurring to formal wording.

1.1. Forced Expulsion

For the purposes of this report, forced expulsion is understood as a set of actions by state authorities whereby a person, after leaving places of deprivation of liberty:

- is effectively deprived of the possibility to freely remain on the territory of their own country;
- is subjected to pressure with the aim of leaving the country;
- is transported to the state border or compelled to cross it;
- is deprived of documents or of the possibility to obtain them;
- has no real choice to remain without the risk of repeated deprivation of liberty.

Forced expulsion may not be accompanied by a formal deportation decision and may not be formalized in accordance with established legal procedures. The absence of a formal act does not negate its coercive nature.

1.2. Forced Exile

Forced exile is a form of forced expulsion in which the state creates conditions under which a person's presence on the territory of the country becomes impossible without a threat to their security, freedom, or life.

Indicators of forced exile include:

- threats of repeated detention;
- blackmail through criminal prosecution;
- pressure exerted through relatives;
- absence of legal status;
- constant surveillance and interference in private life.

Formally, a person may leave the country "voluntarily", however, in substance such departure is not voluntary.

1.3. Legal Vacuum After Release

A legal vacuum is a condition in which a person, after leaving places of deprivation of liberty:

- does not have a clearly defined procedural status;
- does not know whether the criminal case has been terminated;
- remains under the threat of immediate repeated detention;
- is deprived of effective means of legal protection.

The legal vacuum is not a legal error or an accidental gap. Within the analyzed practice, it is used as an instrument of control and pressure, allowing the state to act outside formal procedures.

1.4. Release as a Technical Stage

In this report, the term "release" is used exclusively as a descriptive designation of a person's exit from places of deprivation of liberty and does not imply the restoration of rights, the dropping of charges, or the termination of prosecution.

Release is considered as:

- a technical stage of a repressive operation;
- an intermediate state between deprivation of liberty and forced expulsion;
- an instrument that has no independent humanitarian value.

1.5. External Repression

External repression refers to the continuation of repressive action by the state beyond its territorial boundaries.

It manifests itself in the following ways:

- deprivation of the person's ability to return to the country;

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- preservation of threats of criminal prosecution;
 - pressure exerted through relatives remaining in the country;
 - use of the status of an exile as a form of lifelong restriction of rights.

Thus, repression does not end with a person's release from prison, but merely changes its form and geography.

1.6. Refusal of Exile

Refusal of exile is a situation in which a person released from places of deprivation of liberty refuses to leave the territory of the country despite pressure from the state.

Such cases are of particular significance because they:

- expose the true purpose of "release";
- demonstrate the absence of a real choice;
- lead to the disappearance of a person's legal status;
- are accompanied by intensified repressive measures.

The case of Nikolai Statkevich is the first publicly documented example of refusal of exile and is of fundamental importance for the analysis of the entire practice.

1.7. Release Without Freedom

Release without freedom is a key concept of this report.

It describes a situation in which:

- physical release from places of deprivation of liberty is not accompanied by the restoration of rights;
- freedom is replaced by an obligation to leave the country;
- the state retains control over the person's fate.

It is precisely this condition that constitutes the central object of analysis in this report.

2. Mapping the Mechanism: How the Forced Expulsion of Political Prisoners Is Carried Out

This chapter describes a reproducible state mechanism in which a person's exit from places of deprivation of liberty is used not to restore their rights, but to forcibly remove them beyond the borders of the country. This is not a chain of random violations, but a consistent technique applied to different individuals according to a similar scenario.

2.1. Step One: Politically Motivated Criminal Prosecution

The mechanism begins with the initiation of a criminal case on politically motivated grounds. As a rule, such cases:

- are initiated within the framework of repressive campaigns;
- are accompanied by violations of the right to a fair trial;
- result in sentences that do not comply with the principles of legality and proportionality.

At this stage, the foundation for future pressure is formed: a criminal status that can subsequently be used regardless of whether the person is at liberty or in detention.

2.2. Step Two: Exit from Places of Deprivation of Liberty Without Legal Completion of Status

The next stage is the factual exit of a person from places of deprivation of liberty. The key circumstance is that this exit:

- is not accompanied by the termination of the criminal case;
- does not entail the annulment or review of the sentence;
- does not lead to the expungement of a criminal record;
- is not formalized as a restoration of rights.

The person leaves prison without a clear procedural status, which creates a situation of complete legal uncertainty.

2.3. Step Three: Creation of a Legal Vacuum

The absence of legal completion of status forms a legal vacuum in which:

- the person does not know whether they are considered convicted or released;
- any action by security forces may be presented as "lawful";
- the individual lacks effective means of legal protection.

This vacuum is not a collateral defect or an error. It performs the function of a universal instrument of pressure, allowing the state to act outside formal procedures.

2.4. Step Four: Direct and Indirect Pressure

Against the background of the legal vacuum, pressure is applied to the person, which may include:

- threats of repeated detention;
- warnings about "new cases";
- pressure through relatives;
- constant monitoring and summons;
- refusal to issue or return documents.

The purpose of this stage is to deprive the person of any real choice and to create a situation in which remaining in the country is perceived as dangerous.

2.5. Step Five: Forced Movement to the Border

The next stage is the factual forcing of the person beyond the borders of the country, which may take various forms:

- transportation to the state border under the control of security forces;
- escort to a border crossing point;
- coercion to cross the border without documents or with temporary papers;
- absence of the possibility to return.

Even in cases where a deportation decision is not formally issued, the nature of what is occurring remains coercive.

2.6. Step Six: Consolidation of Exile

After crossing the border, the state undertakes actions aimed at consolidating the exile:

- blocking return;
- maintaining criminal status;
- threats of repeated detention in the event of entry;
- pressure on relatives remaining in the country.

Thus, exile acquires a long-term and temporally undefined character.

2.7. Why This Mechanism Cannot Be Considered Release

The described sequence shows that:

- exit from prison does not mean legal release or restoration of legal status;
- the absence of such status makes the exercise of basic rights and guarantees impossible;
- the repressive impact of the state does not cease, but continues in another form.

Freedom in this case functions as a temporary and conditional state, used to achieve another objective - the removal of a person from the political and social space of the country.

2.8. Systemic Character of the Practice

The repetition of these stages in relation to different individuals, at different times and under similar circumstances, indicates that this is not a matter of random decisions.

It testifies to the existence of a centralized approach, coordinated actions of various state bodies, and the integration of this practice into the overall repressive logic of the state.

Under these conditions, forced expulsion should be regarded not as a set of individual violations, but as an element of state policy being implemented.

3. Factual Practices and Typology of Violations

This chapter summarizes documented actions of state authorities applied to political prisoners after their release from places of deprivation of liberty.

Taken together, these actions form a stable pattern of conduct aimed at the actual forced removal of a person beyond the borders of the country.

It is important to emphasize that each of the described practices, taken separately, may be regarded as an individual human rights violation. However, their repetition, combination, and sequential application indicate not isolated abuses, but a purposeful and coordinated approach on the part of the state.

3.1. Forced Transportation to the State Border

One of the most characteristic practices is the forced transfer of released persons directly to state border crossing points immediately after their release from places of deprivation of liberty, under the control of security forces.

Typical features of this practice include:

- absence of voluntary consent to leave;
- escort by security force personnel;
- delivery directly to state border crossing points;
- actual restriction of the ability to refuse crossing the border.

In a number of cases, the released person is deprived of the possibility to make an independent decision, since any refusal is accompanied by threats of repeated deprivation of liberty.

3.2. Deprivation of Documents and Manipulation of the Right to Identity Documents

Documents certifying identity and citizenship are used as a tool of pressure and control. In particular, the following practices have been documented:

- confiscation of passports before or immediately after release from places of deprivation of liberty;
- refusal to return previously confiscated documents;
- refusal to issue new documents;
- creation of a situation in which a person crosses the border without valid documents.

Such actions not only restrict freedom of movement, but also create a state of legal uncertainty and, in some cases, the factual absence of documents already outside the country.

3.3. De Facto “Release” as a Stage of Forced Departure

In a number of documented cases, the release of political prisoners from places of deprivation of liberty was not accompanied by the restoration of the ability to freely determine their place of residence. According to publications in international media and statements by human rights organizations, released persons were immediately transported under the control of security forces to the state border and effectively removed beyond the borders of the country.

Available evidence indicates that such persons found themselves abroad without valid documents or without the ability to independently determine the further conditions of their stay, while return to the Republic of Belarus was perceived by them as impossible or associated with a high risk of deprivation of liberty¹.

Under these circumstances, departure beyond the borders of the country cannot be regarded as a voluntary exercise of the right to leave, but constitutes a factual continuation of repressive impact, in which physical exit from prison is used as a technical stage of the forced removal of a person from the country.

¹ United Nations Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights (OHCHR). Belarus: UN experts denounce expulsion of citizens, warn about risk of statelessness. Press release, 8 December 2025.

<https://www.ohchr.org/en/press-releases/2025/12/belarus-un-experts-denounce-expulsion-citizens-warn-about-risk-statelessness>

4. The Case of Nikolai Statkevich as a Key Precedent of Refusal of Exile

The case of Nikolai Statkevich is of fundamental importance for understanding the emerging practice of releasing political prisoners in the Republic of Belarus, implemented within the framework of foreign policy arrangements. It was in this episode that, for the first time, a refusal to accept the imposed scenario of completing release through departure beyond the country's borders was recorded, making it possible to reveal the internal limitations and contradictions of the mechanism being applied.

4.1. Context and Conditions of Release

On **21 June 2025**, the Belarusian authorities released the first group of political prisoners, consisting of 14 people. The release was accompanied by their subsequent forced removal from the territory of the Republic of Belarus and was carried out in the context of foreign-policy contacts mediated by the United States of America. These actions were not accompanied by the legal termination of criminal prosecution or the restoration of the legal status of the released persons².

On **11 September 2025**, the Belarusian authorities released a group of 52 political prisoners. The release took place in a similar context of foreign-policy contacts and was accompanied by organized actions of state bodies, including the transportation of the released persons to the state border of the Republic of Belarus³.

The nature of this operation indicates that the release was in fact not treated as the restoration of the legal status of a person within the country, but as a process logically culminating in their departure from the territory of the state. The possibility of remaining in the country within the framework of this procedure was not provided for and was not accompanied by any legal decisions ensuring legal certainty.

4.2. Forced Expulsion as a Reproducible Mechanism

The mass character of the first and second waves of expulsions, their logistical organization and the identity of the actions applied, as well as the subsequent reproduction of this model in the third major wave of releases on **13 December 2025**, during which 123 people were released, make it possible to qualify what occurred not as a one-time episode, but as a reproducible mechanism of forced expulsion embedded in the practice of foreign-policy arrangements⁴.

The release was carried out in conditions of a factual absence of alternatives: former political prisoners were transported to the state border under the control of security forces, and the crossing of the border was regarded as the expected and logically predetermined completion of the procedure. The possibility of remaining on the territory of the country was not envisaged and was not accompanied by any legal decisions ensuring legal certainty of the released person's status.

At the same time, the practice itself was not accompanied by any official legal qualification - neither as deportation nor as any other form of forced removal. The absence of a formalized decision did not eliminate the coercive nature of what was taking place, but, on the contrary, created a space of legal uncertainty in which departure became the only manageable scenario for completing the release.

² Reuters. "Lukashenko frees husband of exiled Belarus opposition leader and 13 others", 21 June 2025. <https://www.reuters.com/world/europe/belarus-opposition-leader-tsikhanouski-freed-jail-his-wife-says-2025-06-21/>

³ Euronews. "Belarus freed 52 prisoners who are now in Lithuania", 11 September 2025, <https://ru.euronews.com/2025/09/11/v-belarusi-osvobodili-52-zaklyuchennyh-oni-uzhe-nahodyatsya-v-litve>

⁴ Associated Press (AP). "Belarus frees 123 prisoners including Nobel Peace Prize laureate Ales Bialiatski and opposition figure Maria Kalesnikava." 13 December 2025. <https://apnews.com/article/39a85ae9a4303974c8c4a23be6d6b858>

The repeatability of the scenario, the absence of legal completion of the status of released persons, and the preservation of the logic of mandatory departure beyond the country's borders confirm that what is involved is not situational decisions, but the application of a stable model implemented according to a predetermined algorithm.

4.3. Nikolai Statkevich's Refusal and the Disruption of the Mechanism's Logic

Nikolai Statkevich refused to cross the state border and leave the territory of the Republic of Belarus. This refusal was of fundamental importance not as an individual act of dissent, but as an event that exposed the structural vulnerability of the entire operation.

The refusal demonstrated that the release was not a legally completed act and did not contain solutions allowing a person to remain in the country with the restoration of legal status.

The mechanism functioned exclusively on the condition of the physical removal of the individual beyond the state's borders. At the moment of refusal, it became evident that the release did not have independent legal value and could not be realized outside the departure scenario.

4.4. Legal Vacuum as a Direct Consequence of the Refusal

As a result of the refusal to depart, Nikolai Statkevich found himself in a state of legal vacuum. After refusing to cross the state border, his actual whereabouts and legal status were not officially confirmed by state authorities.

There is no reliable information as to whether he is at liberty or has again been detained in places of deprivation of liberty.

At the same time, state authorities refused to provide information about his procedural status, which indicates the deliberate creation of a situation of complete legal uncertainty.

4.5. Political and Institutional Inconvenience of the Case

The case of Nikolai Statkevich proved problematic for all parties involved in the process. For the Belarusian authorities, this refusal created the risk of a situation in which the release did not culminate in the departure of the released person beyond the territory of the country. For external partners and intermediaries, the refusal meant the impossibility of considering the operation completed, as the question arose regarding the fate of a person who found himself outside the legal framework following the implementation of the agreements.

Taken together, this formed an objective interest of all parties in minimizing public attention to this episode. This conclusion records the political and communicative complexity of the case, but does not replace the analysis of the reasons for the subsequent inaction, which is addressed in the following chapters.

In the same context, it is necessary to separately identify the role of Belarusian émigré political structures, which are regularly present in the public sphere around the topics of releases, repression, and international negotiations.

Belarusian émigré political structures are not considered within the framework of this report as participants in the process, elements of the mechanism, or independent actors. This is due to the fact that they did not and do not possess functions enabling them to influence decision-making, the formulation of conditions, the course of implementation, or the consequences of the practice of releases and forced expulsions. Their presence was limited to external public and communicative accompaniment of decisions already made and implemented and had no significance for the fate of the released individuals.

4.6. Risks of Managed Pressure After the Refusal

Refusal to depart in conditions of legal vacuum makes the individual vulnerable to subsequent forms of pressure. The state retains the possibility of coercing a repeated departure or applying other repressive measures without the need for a formal revision of the arrangements.

Thus, the refusal reveals not only the vulnerability of a specific individual, but also the limits of manageability of the entire release scheme.

4.7. Significance of the Case for the Analysis of Subsequent Practices

The case of Nikolai Statkevich is the starting point at which the key characteristics of the practice under consideration first manifested themselves:

- absence of legal completion of release;
- impossibility of remaining in the country without risk;
- use of legal uncertainty as an instrument of pressure;
- dependence of the mechanism on the silent acceptance of the exile scenario.

It is precisely this episode that makes it possible to move from the analysis of an individual case to the consideration of a broader question - the limits of applicability of humanitarian and human rights mechanisms under conditions of the continued existence of a repressive structure of power.

5. The Second and Third Waves of Forced Expulsions: Transition from an Episode to a Systemic Practice

The events that followed the first recorded practice of the forced expulsion of politically persecuted individuals were not accompanied by an external fixation of what had occurred as an element of a reproducible mechanism. Regardless of the possible internal intentions of the regime, following this episode there was no advancement, on the part of the United States, of demands aimed at the formalization of release conditions, the legal completion of the status of released individuals, or the introduction of protective mechanisms. Only the repetition of analogous actions during the second wave made it possible to record the reproduction of previously applied elements and raised the question of the formation of a systemic practice.

The events that fully unfolded after the second wave of the forced expulsion of political prisoners and the refusal of Nikolai Statkevich to leave the territory of the Republic of Belarus demonstrated that the mechanisms identified in September were not revised, adjusted, or limited. On the contrary, the absence of an institutional response to the identified violations led to their reproduction in an expanded and more stable format.

5.1. Absence of Review and Correction of the Mechanism after the Second Wave of Expulsions

The case of Mikalai Statkevich and the second group of released individuals revealed key defects of the applied practice:

- absence of a legally finalized status for the released persons;
- absence of the right to remain in the country without the threat of renewed violence;
- use of release as a stage of a logistical operation for removal;
- absence of international monitoring after release from places of deprivation of liberty.

Despite the public nature of the precedent and its international resonance, none of these defects were eliminated. No new requirements were developed, no additional conditions were introduced, and no guarantees were fixed for persons released subsequently.

Thus, the second wave did not become a point of revision of the practice, but was perceived as an acceptable model that entailed no negative consequences for the organizers of the process.

5.2. Reproduction of the Scheme without Changes

The third wave of forced expulsions demonstrated a complete reproduction of the previously recorded mechanism. Release once again took place outside the framework of rights restoration; individuals did not receive a clearly defined legal status, and departure from the country was regarded as an expected and de facto mandatory completion of the procedure. Refusal to leave continued to mean the persistence of the risk of renewed persecution.

A key circumstance is that after the second wave, the United States of America, with the participation of the European Union, did not use the negotiating resources available to them to advance principled conditions aimed at eliminating the identified defects of the release mechanism. No demands were put forward regarding the legal finalization of the status of released persons, the right to remain on the territory of the country without the threat of renewed violence, or guarantees of safety after release from places of deprivation of liberty.

The absence of such conditions allowed the regime to preserve the original model without changes. As a result, the third wave of expulsions became not an exception and not a repetition of an accidental scenario, but a direct continuation of the previously applied practice, implemented already in conditions of the absence of external constraints and corrective requirements.

5.3. Formation of Systemic Character

If the first wave could be perceived as a one-off episode lacking institutional weight, the repetition of analogous actions during the second wave recorded the reproducibility of the applied mechanism. The identity of procedures, the absence of legal completion of the status of released individuals, and the preservation of the coercive nature of departure testified to a transition from isolated application to a stable repressive practice.

The absence of reaction and corrective measures after the second wave, despite the obvious nature of the identified defects of the mechanism, created the conditions for its further scaling. During the third wave, release definitively ceased to be exceptional in nature and was transformed into a stable, managed channel of external pressure embedded within a broader political process. Thus, the systemic character of this practice was formed not at the moment of the first episode, but as a result of the absence of an institutional reaction after the fixation of the mechanism's reproducibility, which ensured its further reproduction without change⁵.

5.4. Loss of the Possibility of Influence through Negotiations

The absence of correction of the identified mechanism after the Statkevich case led to a qualitative change in the situation. If at the moment of the second wave there still existed an opportunity to revise conditions, formulate additional requirements, and introduce protective mechanisms, then after the reproduction of the practice in the third wave, the space for negotiating influence sharply narrowed.

From this moment:

- the regime received confirmation of the permissibility of expulsions;
- release was finally separated from the restoration of rights;
- negotiation processes lost the capacity to influence the fate of specific individuals;
- the format of releases continued to be applied in its previous form and was not subjected to legal correction.

In other words, the third wave demonstrated that negotiations ceased to be a mechanism for preventing violations and became a background for their repetition.

5.5. Expansion of the Circle of Vulnerable Persons

The systemic nature of the practice means that not individual figures, but all persons falling under the category of politically persecuted individuals are exposed to the threat of forced expulsion. The absence of fixed rights and procedures creates a situation in which each subsequent released person is treated not as a subject of law, but as an object of a logistical operation.

This leads to:

- growth of legal uncertainty;
- intensification of psychological pressure on prisoners and their families;
- normalization of exile as a form of repression;
- reduction of opportunities for international protection.

5.6. Conclusion

The third wave of forced expulsions became a direct consequence of the unrealized precedent of the second. Mikalai Statkevich's refusal of exile exposed the vulnerability of the system; however, the absence of an institutional response led not to its dismantling, but to its consolidation.

Thus, the transition from the second wave to the third should be viewed not as a chain of unrelated events, but as a process of formation of a stable practice in which a person's release from places of deprivation of liberty is used not to terminate repressive impact against released individuals, but to transform it into forced expulsion, exclusion of the person from the internal legal space, and retention outside the country under the threat of renewed persecution.

The repeatability of this practice indicates that the absence of correction of the mechanism is linked not only to the political decisions of the parties, but also to the limited capacity of external actors to influence the conditions of the implementation of releases within the country.

⁵ United Nations Human Rights Council, Conference Room Paper of the Group of Independent Experts on Belarus, A/HRC/60/CRP.1, 4 February 2025, paras. 81, 103 and 105.

<https://www.ohchr.org/sites/default/files/documents/hrbodies/hrcouncil/ohchrbelarus/a-hrc-60-crp-1-english-version.pdf>

6. Legal Vacuum as an Instrument for the Continuation of Repression

6.1. The Concept of a Legal Vacuum in the Context of Releases

The key feature of the practice of forced expulsions of political prisoners from the Republic of Belarus is not the very fact of removing people beyond the country's borders, but the absence of a legally completed status after the so-called release.

A situation arises in which a person:

- ceases to be held in places of deprivation of liberty, but does not receive any procedural decision confirming the termination of criminal prosecution;
- is not recognized as released with the restoration of civil and political rights;
- does not have a clear and confirmed legal status.

Such a condition should be qualified as a legal vacuum - a deliberately created zone of uncertainty in which a person is deprived of legal protection both within the state and beyond its borders.

6.2. Absence of Legal Completion as a Systemic Feature

In all recorded cases of release accompanied by subsequent removal, the following mandatory elements of legal completion are absent:

- termination of the criminal case;
- annulment or review of the sentence;
- official rehabilitation;
- restoration of restricted rights;
- issuance of documents confirming a change of status.

Thus, the release is not formalized as a legal act, but exists exclusively as a physical termination of detention, which does not entail legal consequences in favor of the released person⁶.

This fundamentally distinguishes this practice from:

- release upon completion of the sentence;
- release by court decision;
- release within the framework of procedural mechanisms.

6.3. Legal Vacuum as a Form of Violence

The absence of status is not a neutral condition. On the contrary, it is used as an active instrument of pressure and control.

Under conditions of a legal vacuum, a person:

- cannot challenge the actions of the state;
- does not have access to mechanisms of legal protection;
- cannot confirm the legality of their position;
- remains vulnerable to repeated detention or other forms of coercion.

Thus, the legal vacuum performs the function of continuing repression outside places of deprivation of liberty⁷. Repression does not cease - it merely changes its form, becoming less visible but no less effective.

6.4. Forced Expulsion as the Only Way to “Complete” the Release

Analysis of practice shows that, in the logic of the Belarusian authorities, a release is considered completed only in one case - upon the physical crossing of the border.

⁶ UN Human Rights Council, Report of the Group of Independent Experts on the situation of human rights in Belarus, A/HRC/60/CRP.1, 2025, paras. 81 and 103.

<https://www.ohchr.org/sites/default/files/documents/hrbodies/hrcouncil/ohchrbelarus/a-hrc-60-crp-1-english-version.pdf>

⁷ UN Human Rights Council, Report of the Group of Independent Experts on the situation of human rights in Belarus, A/HRC/60/CRP.1, 2025, para. 105.

<https://www.ohchr.org/sites/default/files/documents/hrbodies/hrcouncil/ohchrbelarus/a-hrc-60-crp-1-english-version.pdf>

Until the moment of departure, the person remains a problem for the system. The very fact of refusing to leave makes it impossible to “close” the operation, since there is no alternative legal scenario.

This means that:

- the right to remain in the country is not provided for;
- disagreement with departure has no procedural mechanism;
- refusal automatically transfers the person into a zone of increased risk.

This is precisely why the legal vacuum is a deliberately embedded element of the scheme, rather than its side effect.

6.5. Universality of the Mechanism: From an Individual Case to a System

The case of Nikolai Statkevich was the first to clearly demonstrate the existence of a legal vacuum as a key element of the entire construction. The third wave of expulsions showed that this mechanism was not reviewed, corrected, or eliminated.

Despite the revealed precedent:

- legal procedures were not refined;
- guarantees were not introduced;
- the right to remain in the country was not secured;
- the status of released persons was never defined.

This led to the reproduction of the same model in the third wave, but already in a mass and systemic format.

6.6. Functions of the Legal Vacuum in the Repressive System

The legal vacuum simultaneously performs several functions:

Instrument of pressure - a person is forced to agree to departure as the only way to minimize risk.

Means of neutralization - active and principled individuals are removed from the internal space of the country.

Mechanism of foreign-policy maneuvering - the absence of legal decisions allows flexibility to be preserved in negotiations and responsibility to be denied.

Form of concealment of repression - the absence of a formal status complicates the international qualification of what is happening.

Thus, the legal vacuum is not a defect of the system, but a consciously used element of it.

6.7. Consequences for International Actors

The legal vacuum affects not only the released persons, but also external partners, since it:

- creates a new category of people without a clear status;
- shifts the burden of legalization and protection onto receiving states;
- makes the standard application of international procedures impossible;
- undermines trust in international mechanisms of protection and response.

As a result, international actors are forced to respond to the consequences without having instruments of influence over the root cause.

6.8. Conclusion

The legal vacuum after release is a central element of the modern practice of forced expulsions from the Republic of Belarus.

It:

- is not accidental;
- is used as a form of continuation of repression;
- makes coercion possible without formal violence;
- ensures the reproducibility of the system.

Understanding this mechanism is a necessary condition for analyzing subsequent waves of expulsions and for developing effective international responses.

7. Forced Expulsion as a Form of External Repression

7.1. From Internal Repression to External Coercion

Traditionally, repression is associated with deprivation of liberty, restriction of rights, and physical violence within the state. However, the practice that took shape in the Republic of Belarus in 2025 demonstrates a different model of repression, carried beyond the territory of the country while preserving its political and disciplinary function.

The forced expulsion of political prisoners after formal release is not the termination of repression, but its continuation in another form - through exile, legal uncertainty, and dependence on external actors.

7.2. Expulsion without Deportation: The Essence of the Mechanism

The key feature of the practice under consideration is the absence of a formal deportation procedure. The state does not adopt decisions on expulsion in the legal sense, does not formalize corresponding acts, and does not recognize the very fact of exile.

In practice, the following scheme is implemented:

- the person is released without legal completion of status;
- under the control of security structures, the person is transported to the border;
- crossing the border becomes the only way to avoid immediate renewed pressure;
- the state retains the ability to deny the coercive nature of the departure.

This construction allows repression to exist outside the language of law, which significantly complicates its international qualification.

7.3. The Forced Nature of Departure

Despite the formal absence of an order of expulsion, the departure is of a forced nature, since:

- refusal to cross the border is not procedurally provided for;
- guarantees of safety upon return are absent;
- the threat of repeated detention remains;
- the legal vacuum renders the person completely vulnerable.

Thus, this is not a matter of freedom of movement, but of coercion into exile, implemented outside a legal procedure and contrary to international human rights standards.

7.4. External Repression as an Element of State Policy

Expulsion performs several functions that go beyond individual impact:

Cleansing of the internal space - active and principled figures are physically removed from the country without the need for their prolonged detention in places of deprivation of liberty;

Disruption of social and political ties - deprivation of the ability to remain within society destroys horizontal connections and reduces the potential for internal resistance;

Export of the problem - responsibility for the further fate of individuals is effectively shifted onto receiving states and international structures;

Control through vulnerability - the absence of documents, status, and guarantees makes expelled persons dependent and manageable.

7.5. From Individual Pressure to Systemicity

After the first identified precedent of refusal of exile (the case of Nikolai Statkevich), the scheme was not revised. On the contrary, in the subsequent wave of releases, the same elements were reproduced:

- absence of legal completion;
- organized removal;
- absence of an alternative to departure;
- absence of international guarantees.

This indicates a transition from isolated operations to a stable repressive practice embedded in the system of foreign-policy maneuvering.

7.6. Consequences for Expelled Persons

For the expelled persons themselves, this practice means:

- loss of the right to live in their own country;
- absence of choice and consent;
- vulnerability in legal and social terms;
- the need for emergency legalization without documents;
- a prolonged state of uncertainty and dependence.

Thus, expulsion becomes a form of punishment comparable in its consequences to deprivation of liberty, but lacking formal recognition.

7.7. International Legal Significance

From the perspective of international law, forced expulsion without a formal procedure:

- violates the right of a person to remain in their own country;
- creates a risk of statelessness;
- undermines the principle of legal certainty;
- blurs state responsibility.

Taken together with the legal vacuum, this practice forms a new type of repression requiring separate international qualification.

7.8. Conclusion

The forced expulsion of political prisoners after release constitutes:

- a continuation of repression outside the territory of the state;
- an instrument of political pressure;
- a means of circumventing international obligations;
- a stable and reproducible practice.

Understanding this form of external repression makes it possible to proceed to an analysis of systemic consequences for Europe and international human rights protection mechanisms, as well as to the development of practical responses to this threat.

8. A Consciously Unrealized Precedent: Reasons for the Non-Application of the Nikolai Statkevich Case and the Formation of a Systemic Practice of Expulsions

8.1. The Statkevich Case as a Moment of Possible Correction of the Mechanism

Nikolai Statkevich's refusal to leave the territory of the Republic of Belarus after being released from places of deprivation of liberty within the framework of the second wave of diplomatic arrangements became the first publicly recorded case of disagreement with a release model providing for subsequent forced expulsion⁸.

For the first time, a scenario was implemented in which a political prisoner did not complete the release procedure by crossing the state border. This made it possible to identify a key vulnerability of the entire scheme being applied.

For the first time, it opened a concrete possibility to reassess and correct the mechanism, including the following aspects:

- establish that departure is not a voluntary element of the procedure;
- identify the absence of a legally formalized status of a person released from places of deprivation of liberty without an obligation to leave the country;
- raise the question of the permissibility of such a person's presence on the territory of the Republic of Belarus;
- prevent the transformation of political arrangements into a stable practice of forced expulsion.

However, this precedent did not receive institutional development and was left without a legal and political response.

8.2. Coincidence of Interests of the Parties as a Cause of Inaction

The absence of a response to the Statkevich case was not the result of a technical error or a misunderstanding. It was the result of a convergence of factors and interests of the parties involved in the process of releases and subsequent expulsions, under which the formalization and consolidation of this precedent did not receive further development.

The present episode makes it possible to pose a broader question - not only about the nature of the recorded practice, but also about the limits of applicability of existing human rights and diplomatic mechanisms under the continued existence of the current power structure.

The limits of applicability of existing human rights and diplomatic mechanisms are manifested in the objective inability of external actors to ensure the protection of a person remaining within a repressive system.

8.3. Position of the Belarusian Regime: Prevention of a Precedent and Managed Legal Uncertainty

For the Belarusian authorities, the realization of the Statkevich case would have meant the creation of an extremely dangerous precedent - the recognition of the fact that a free political prisoner exists inside the country after release.

Such a development would have created a number of risks:

- the emergence of a chain reaction of refusals to leave the country by other persons extracted places of deprivation of liberty;
- the undermining of the logic of "cleansing" the internal space of politically active figures;
- the emergence of an alternative center of political subjectivity within the country;
- the loss of control over the release mechanism used as an instrument of foreign policy bargaining.

⁸ The Guardian - Belarus prisoners released under US deal describe confusion and forced deportations (12 September 2025)

<https://www.theguardian.com/world/2025/sep/12/belarus-prisoners-released-lithuania-us-deal-confused-forced-deportations>

Thus, the situation does not concern a confirmed state of freedom nor legally formalized detention, but rather a situation in which state authorities consciously refuse to inform the spouse about the fate of a person under their control.

Such practice indicates the deliberate use of legal uncertainty as an instrument of pressure and exclusion of an individual from the public and legal sphere. It demonstrates that refusal to accept the logic of forced expulsion does not lead to correction of the mechanism, but, on the contrary, results in its tightening.

8.4. The position of external negotiating actors: limits of influence and real constraints.

8.4.1. The United States of America: the key negotiating actor and the limits of political pressure

The United States of America is regarded as the key external negotiating actor that played a leading role in establishing and maintaining contacts with the Belarusian authorities and possessed the greatest capacity to influence the parameters and conditions of releases. In this capacity, for the United States, recognition of the case of Nikolai Statkevich would have required acknowledging a structural defect in the entire negotiation framework being applied.

The refusal to leave clearly demonstrated that the agreements reached:

- do not ensure the restoration of freedom as a legal status;
- are conditional in nature and presuppose the preservation of elements of coercion;
- do not contain security guarantees for individuals remaining on the territory of the Republic of Belarus after being released from places of deprivation of liberty.

The implementation of this precedent would objectively have required the American side to:

- revise the negotiation procedures within which the release and subsequent departure were carried out;
- advance additional, mandatory, and publicly recorded conditions and guarantees aimed at eliminating the identified defects of the mechanism, including the absence of legal finalization of the status of released persons and the coercive nature of departure;
- establish international monitoring mechanisms;
- acknowledge the risk of systemic human rights violations embedded in the existing practice.

At the same time, the absence of a reaction on the part of the United States cannot be explained exclusively by political disinterest, formalism, or a desire to preserve negotiating comfort. What was at stake was a deeper factor - an awareness of the limits of applicability of the existing negotiating and diplomatic instruments under conditions of the continued existence of an active repressive regime.

The implementation of the Statkevich case went beyond the framework of a mediation-based negotiation model, as it required interference in the internal legal status of the individual and de facto recognition of a scenario in which a released person remains on the territory of the Republic of Belarus without subsequent departure. This, in turn, would have required ensuring minimum guarantees of security and legal certainty for that individual, as well as organizing monitoring and protection not at the border, but inside the repressive system.

Recognition of this precedent would have implied a qualitative change in the role of the external actor - a transition from the function of mediator to that of guarantor. Such a transition would have entailed assuming responsibility for the individual's security, the need to respond to possible re-arrest or disappearance, and the formation of obligations that cannot be ensured in the absence of access and coercive enforcement mechanisms within the country. This inaction does not constitute legal complicity; however, it is of substantial significance for assessing the political responsibility of external actors in the context of preserving and reproducing this practice.

An additional factor was the understanding that the defective negotiation framework, despite all its shortcomings, was in fact functioning and made it possible to secure the release of individual persons from places of deprivation of liberty.

Under these conditions, the regime preferred a scenario in which Nikolai Statkevich was kept in a state of complete legal uncertainty - without official recognition of freedom and without legal formalization of a new status.

At the time of preparation of this report, there is no reliable information regarding his whereabouts or legal status. The only written response received by Nikolai Statkevich's spouse from the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Belarus contains a direct refusal to provide information about his location or procedural status (**see Appendix**).

Recognition of the Statkevich case would have placed the American side before a choice between preserving an imperfect but effective channel and adopting a principled position capable of leading to its complete blockage without any guarantee of subsequent releases.

In assessing the possible consequences, the logic of the Belarusian regime - which does not allow the existence of free political prisoners inside the country - was also taken into account. In this context, entrenching the refusal to leave could have led not to an expansion of the freedom of a particular individual, but to an escalation of pressure, demonstrative punishment, or the closure of negotiation channels, which would objectively have worsened his situation.

As a result, none of the measures listed above were implemented. A path of silence was chosen, under which the case of Nikolai Statkevich did not receive official status, and the negotiation framework continued to function without changes.

8.4.2. The European Union: a supporting and secondary actor

The European Union, within the framework of the process under consideration, acted as a secondary participant in the political-diplomatic contour of the releases, not serving as a leading initiator of the negotiations and not determining the parameters of the practical implementation of the mechanism. It did not possess its own instruments allowing it to influence the conditions of the releases or to compel the Belarusian authorities to eliminate the identified violations.

In this context, the case of Nikolai Statkevich revealed a key defect of the negotiation scheme: the absence of a legally formalized release and a practice in which the cessation of pressure was factually linked to the mandatory departure beyond the borders of the country. The realization of this precedent (that is, recognition of the possibility to remain on the territory of the Republic of Belarus after release and the provision of minimal guarantees of security and legal certainty) would have required the organization of constant monitoring and protection inside the repressive system, rather than at the border. Such actions objectively lay beyond the institutional capacities of the European Union.

In contrast to the United States as the leading negotiating subject, the European Union did not possess an independent negotiation channel or resources allowing it to impose on the Belarusian authorities mandatory conditions for correcting the mechanism, including the legal completion of the status of released persons and security guarantees in the event of refusal to depart.

This differentiation is used exclusively for analytical purposes and is aimed at a correct assessment of the institutional role and political responsibility of external parties. It does not substitute the legal responsibility of the state - the initiator of repression and does not equate diplomatic participation or negotiation mediation with complicity in human rights violations.

8.5. Tacit consent as a mechanism for entrenching the violation

The convergence of the parties' factual positions led not to the resolution of the situation, but to its entrenchment.

The failure to implement the case of Nikolai Statkevich meant:

- recognition of the admissibility of legal uncertainty;
- acceptance of the coercive nature of departure;
- consent to the reproduction of a defective mechanism.

Refusal to leave was excluded from the set of permissible scenarios. Expulsion became established as the standard and non-alternative final outcome of negotiated releases.

8.6. Formation of systemic practice: the third wave as a consequence of unmade decisions

The procedure was not revised. The legal vacuum was preserved as an element of the mechanism⁹. The absence of a response to the Statkevich case led to the direct reproduction of the scheme in the subsequent wave of releases.

This led to the following:

- expulsion became the norm;
- the conditions of release ceased to be discussed;
- each released person was placed before a non-alternative choice;
- legal uncertainty was transformed into an instrument of pressure.

8.7. Theoretical measures that could have prevented the emergence of a stable practice of forced expulsions at an early stage

The formation of a stable practice of forced expulsions could theoretically have been prevented through the implementation of the following measures:

- recognition of refusal to leave the country as an acceptable scenario;
- legal formalization of the status of a person released without an obligation to leave the country;
- mandatory legal completion of the individual's status prior to expulsion, including the termination of criminal prosecution in any procedural form and the return of personal documents;
- public fixation of the case of Nikolai Statkevich as a mandatory precedent within the negotiation process;
- initiation of an international monitoring mechanism in exceptional cases of refusal to be expelled, including the establishment of the person's whereabouts, guaranteed access to the individual, legal formalization of the released person's status, and subsequent monitoring of the observance of their rights on the territory of the Republic of Belarus.

The measures listed above delineate the limits of possible adjustment of the mechanism within existing negotiation and human rights approaches. Their absence led to the preservation of a defective model in which release did not signify the restoration of rights but was instead used as a form of controlled removal from the country.

The theoretical model for terminating the practice of forced expulsions was initially considered as logically deriving from the identified violations and consistent with international legal standards¹⁰. Within the framework of this report, it was used as the primary working hypothesis, subject to verification through the analysis of actual practices, the institutional context, and specific cases. The conducted research demonstrated that, under the existing conditions, this model cannot be implemented. The identified circumstances indicate its structural incompatibility with the functioning of a repressive system of power, within which legal guarantees are conditional and revocable in nature and do not provide real protection.

As a result, the theoretical model retains its significance as an analytical reference point and evaluative criterion; however, it failed to become a practical instrument, which led to a revision and modification of the final conclusions of this report.

8.8. Conclusion

The case of Nikolai Statkevich demonstrated that the practice of forced expulsion could have been halted at an early stage. The refusal to leave revealed a structural defect in the release

⁹ The Washington Post, "Belarusian authorities have freed 123 prisoners, including Nobel Peace Prize laureate Ales Bialiatski and key opposition figures", 13 December 2025
<https://www.washingtonpost.com/world/2025/12/13/belarus-releases-political-prisoners/>

¹⁰ UN Human Rights Council - Report of the Special Rapporteur on the situation of human rights in Belarus, A/HRC/59/59 (22 April 2025), para. 88 (a), (b), (e), (g), (n)
<https://docs.un.org/en/A/HRC/59/59>

mechanism - the absence of legal finalization of status and a situation in which pressure ceased only after the actual departure of the released individual from the country.

The lack of response to this precedent led not to the correction of the identified violations, but to the consolidation of the existing scheme. The third wave of expulsions became a direct consequence of the fact that, after the second wave, participants in the negotiation process failed to use the opportunity that had emerged to revise the mechanism and did not advance conditions aimed at eliminating its key defects. Release ultimately ceased to signify the restoration of rights and was institutionalized as a form of controlled removal of politically inconvenient individuals from the country.

The non-application of the Statkevich case is explained not only by the logic of the parties' behavior within the already established mechanism, but also by the objective limits of existing negotiation and human rights instruments. These instruments were not originally designed to ensure legal certainty and the safety of an individual remaining within a sovereign repressive regime, nor did they envisage the assumption of responsibility for that individual's subsequent fate.

Recognition of this precedent would have required moving beyond mediation and transitioning to the role of guarantor - with the provision of legal status, monitoring, and protection of the individual within the country. Such a transition proved institutionally and politically impossible for external actors.

The preservation of the original model made it possible to continue releases without altering the regime's internal control mechanism, while simultaneously rendering the practice of forced expulsions stable and reproducible. The third wave thus became a logical continuation of the second, rather than a random development of events.

9. International Consequences and Complicity through Inaction

9.1. Transformation of Repression into a Transboundary Problem

The systemic practice of forced expulsions and the subsequent disappearance of individuals who refused exile move the repression of the Republic of Belarus beyond the limits of its internal jurisdiction. This concerns not only violations of human rights within the country, but the formation of a transboundary repressive model whose consequences directly affect receiving states, international organizations, and intermediaries involved in negotiation and human rights processes¹¹.

Release through expulsion does not end repression - it relocates it into the external sphere, shifting risks, responsibility, as well as legal and social consequences onto third parties.

9.2. The Role of Intermediaries and the Effect of Tacit Consent

International intermediaries participating in negotiations on the release of political prisoners de facto become elements of the mechanism if they:

- do not insist on the legal finalization of the status of those released;
- do not demand guarantees of the right to remain in the country;
- do not respond to refusals to depart;
- do not record cases of legal vacuum and disappearances.

The absence of a public response to the case of Nikolai Statkevich and the subsequent wave of expulsions formed tacit consent¹² to the following assumptions:

- release is possible only on the condition of exile;
- punishment for refusing exile is accepted as a given;
- the disappearance of a person within the country does not require immediate international intervention.

Thus, legal mechanisms were deformed into an instrument of managed repression.

9.3. Responsibility of Receiving States

Receiving states face direct consequences of the practice of forced expulsion of political prisoners, manifested as follows:

1. Absence of a legally finalized status for expelled persons.

Individuals arrive without a clear procedural position: they are not rehabilitated, not recognized as released in a legal sense, and do not possess documents confirming the termination of criminal prosecution.

2. Legal uncertainty and administrative burden.

The receiving side is forced to make non-standard and accelerated decisions regarding legalization, asylum, or temporary stay without a clear legal basis, which creates risks of violations of national and international law.

3. Shifting responsibility away from the state that is the source of repression.

The state of origin effectively evades responsibility for the fate of released persons, transferring humanitarian, legal, and social consequences onto receiving countries.

4. Risks of continued pressure on expelled persons.

There remains a threat of renewed pressure through threats to relatives, deprivation of citizenship, denial of documents, and other forms of transboundary influence.

¹¹ UN Human Rights Council, Report of the Special Rapporteur on the situation of human rights in Belarus, A/HRC/59/59 (22 April 2025), §84.
<https://docs.un.org/en/A/HRC/59/59>

¹² UN OHCHR press release, “Belarus: Freeing political prisoners does not end policy of repression”, 17 December 2025.
<https://www.ohchr.org/en/press-releases/2025/12/belarus-freeing-political-prisoners-does-not-end-policy-repression-warns-un>

5. Political and diplomatic risks.

The receiving state becomes involved in the consequences of another state's repressive practice, including potential international disputes, accusations of complicity, or legitimization of this practice.

Conclusion:

Ignoring the source and the coercive nature of departure turns receiving states into passive participants in a chain of violations, regardless of declared intentions. This shifts responsibility away from the state that initiated the repression and contributes to the institutionalization of expulsions as an acceptable instrument of political pressure.

9.4. Undermining International Human Rights Protection Mechanisms

The systemic nature of expulsions and the absence of a response to Statkevich's refusal undermine several fundamental principles of international law at once:

- the right of a person to remain in their own country;
- the prohibition of forcible exile;
- the principle of legal certainty;
- the obligation of the state to inform about the fate of a detained person.

When such violations do not receive legal qualification or response, a dangerous precedent is created: repressive regimes receive a signal that pushing opponents across borders is an acceptable alternative to detention¹³.

9.5. From Negotiated Releases to the Normalization of Exile

The absence of a firm international position led to a shift in the framework of what is permissible¹⁴:

- expulsion ceases to be regarded as an exception;
- disappearances cease to be regarded as an extraordinary violation;
- the legal vacuum ceases to be regarded as grounds for urgent intervention.

As a result, releases carried out in a negotiation context lost their original meaning and became an instrument for legitimizing exile as a form of political governance.

9.6. Conclusion

The established practice shows that:

- forced expulsion has become a stable element of repressive policy;
- ignoring the first precedent (the Statkevich case) led to systemic repetition;
- international intermediaries and structures bear responsibility for the absence of correction of the mechanism;
- without a clear response, disappearances and legal vacuum will be reproduced.

It is precisely at this stage that the need arises to move from describing violations to formulating concrete international demands and response mechanisms.

¹³ UN Human Rights Committee, General Comment No. 27 (Freedom of Movement), CCPR/C/21/Rev.1/Add.9, paras. 19, 21.
<https://www.refworld.org/docid/45139c394.html>

¹⁴ United Nations, Updated Set of Principles for the Protection and Promotion of Human Rights Through Action to Combat Impunity, UN Doc. E/CN.4/2005/102/Add.1 (8 Feb. 2005). Principle 1, p. 7; Principles 2, 19-20, pp. 7, 13.
<https://docs.un.org/en/E/CN.4/2005/102/Add.1>

10. Conclusions: Termination of the Practice of Forced Expulsions- the Normative Model and the Limits of Its Implementation

10.1. The normative model for ending forced expulsions

The termination of the practice of forced expulsions is possible only under a combination of conditions that ensure the genuine restoration of the rights of released persons and exclude the use of departure as a means of continuing repression

This refers to a theoretical model based on the operation of international legal standards and presupposing that the regime is prepared to comply with external obligations and to allow mechanisms for monitoring their observance.

Within such a model, the release of a person from places of deprivation of liberty would imply:

1. Universal rights applicable to all released persons regardless of their subsequent choice (departure or remaining in the country):

- termination of criminal prosecution in a manner resulting in the full and unconditional cessation of all criminal charges;
- prohibition of repeated deprivation of liberty on the same grounds¹⁵;
- absence of any obligation to leave the territory of the state as a condition of release¹⁶;
- restoration of civil and procedural rights;
- elimination of a legal vacuum and indeterminate status after release;
- issuance of official documentation confirming the person's legal status, ensuring the elimination of legal uncertainty after release and enabling recognition and use in cross-border and international contexts (This concerns a practical necessity to eliminate legal uncertainty after release, given that existing international standards do not contain a direct obligation or a clear mechanism for determining legal status.).

2. Guarantees for persons remaining on the territory of the state.

In the theoretical model for terminating expulsions, refusal to leave should be regarded as a permissible choice of the released person that does not entail negative consequences, including the following guarantees:

- prohibition of any pressure for refusing to cross the border;
- guarantees of physical and personal security;
- inadmissibility of replacing criminal prosecution with administrative measures or other forms of non-judicial pressure;
- preservation of access to normal civilian life;
- presence of international monitoring and control mechanisms inside the country

3. Guarantees for persons voluntarily leaving the country.

For persons deciding to depart, the normative model would imply:

- confirmed voluntariness of departure;
- a legally viable status enabling legalization in receiving states;
- protection from transborder persecution;
- removal of the legal and humanitarian burden from receiving countries.

Taken together, these elements constitute a system in which release would not turn into exile, and forced expulsion would lose its systemic character.

10.2. Practical conditions for implementing the normative model

Implementation of the described normative model would be possible only in the presence of

¹⁵ UN Human Rights Committee. General Comment No. 35: Liberty and security of person (Article 9 ICCPR) UN Doc. CCPR/C/GC/35, paras. 17
<https://docs.un.org/en/CCPR/C/GC/35>

¹⁶ UN Human Rights Committee. General Comment No. 27: Freedom of movement (Article 12 ICCPR) UN Doc. CCPR/C/21/Rev.1/Add.9, paras. 19
<https://docs.un.org/en/CCPR/C/21/Rev.1/Add.9>

stable practical mechanisms of control and enforcement that go beyond one-off agreements and political statements¹⁷.

Such conditions would include:

- permanent international presence within the country ensuring monitoring of the fate of released persons;
- mechanisms for rapid response to violations, including immediate documentation of pressure, repeated detentions or disappearances;
- guaranteed and unhindered access for lawyers, human rights defenders and international observers;
- automatic and predictable consequences for the regime in case of non-compliance with undertaken obligations;
- the ability of international actors not only to negotiate, but also to ensure implementation of achieved agreements.

In the absence of these elements, the normative model loses practical applicability and cannot serve as a tool for terminating repressive practice. Under such conditions, any formal guarantees remain declarative and do not provide actual protection for released persons.

10.3. Why the mechanism for protecting released political prisoners does not function inside Belarus?

Analysis of the Belarusian context shows that the described normative model cannot be implemented within the country while the existing structure of power and control is preserved¹⁸.

The problem lies not in the unreality of the model, but in the fact that this protection mechanism is fundamentally incompatible with the existence of a repressive regime that fully controls law enforcement and uses law as an instrument of pressure.

The case of Nikolai Statkevich demonstrated this in practice and became an empirical test of the ultimate limits of any such construction. His refusal to leave revealed the absence of any alternative scenario of release inside the country as such.

A formally released person remaining on the territory of the Republic of Belarus immediately found themselves outside the framework of legal certainty - without a protected status¹⁹, without guaranteed rights²⁰, and without external protection mechanisms.

Practice has shown that:

- a scenario of release without subsequent departure is not provided for by the system and is not permitted by it;
- any person refusing to leave is automatically transferred into a zone of legal vacuum and heightened risk;
- formal legal decisions lose significance at the moment they conflict with political expediency;

¹⁷ United Nations, The rule of law and transitional justice in conflict and post-conflict societies, Report of the Secretary-General, UN Doc. S/2004/616, para. 23.
<https://docs.un.org/en/S/2004/616>

¹⁸ United Nations, The rule of law and transitional justice in conflict and post-conflict societies, Report of the Secretary-General, UN Doc. S/2004/616, paras. 19, 27.
<https://docs.un.org/en/S/2004/616>

¹⁹ Observatory for the Protection of Human Rights Defenders (FIDH-OMCT), “Belarus: Release of political prisoners is a necessary but insufficient step - all arbitrarily detained human rights defenders must be released,” Statement, 15 December 2025, para. beginning “While their release brings long-overdue relief..., the Observatory stresses that this step remains insufficient as long as hundreds... remain arbitrarily detained... and repressions... continue unabated.”
<https://www.fidh.org/en/region/europe-central-asia/belarus/belarus-release-of-political-prisoners-is-a-necessary-but>

²⁰ Observatory for the Protection of Human Rights Defenders (FIDH-OMCT), “Belarus: Release of political prisoners is a necessary but insufficient step - all arbitrarily detained human rights defenders must be released,” Statement, 15 December 2025, para. beginning “The authorities must also ensure full rehabilitation, including the quashing of convictions and restoration of civil and political rights...”.
<https://www.fidh.org/en/region/europe-central-asia/belarus/belarus-release-of-political-prisoners-is-a-necessary-but>

- international actors lack instruments for rapid response and real intervention inside the country.

Under these conditions, the mere existence of a legally completed status does not ensure protection and does not limit arbitrariness. Status exists only as long as it does not conflict with the interests of coercive and political control, after which it can be ignored, revised or nullified without any consequences for the regime.

Thus, the failure of the model is explained not by flaws in its formulation or insufficient firmness of the international position, but by the structural nature of a system of power in which law is subordinated to political discretion, and any guarantees are revocable and conditional.

Interim conclusion.

In the conditions of the Republic of Belarus, observance of even formally recognized guarantees of security and legal status for persons remaining inside the country is structurally impossible, regardless of the level of international pressure or agreements reached.

10.4. The limits of international pressure and the factor of external regime protection

International practice shows that the status of a head of state is not an absolute guarantee of immunity. In certain cases, authoritarian leaders have lost protection of their position and become objects of external pressure and criminal prosecution, including through extraterritorial mechanisms (Manuel Noriega (Panama)²¹ and Nicolás Maduro (Venezuela)²²).

However, such scenarios are possible only in the presence of a combination of factors that are absent in the Belarusian context.

The regime of Alexander Lukashenko fundamentally differs from a number of other authoritarian regimes in that its stability over decades has been ensured by constant political, economic and coercive support from the Russian Federation²³.

The events of 2020 clearly demonstrated that preservation of the existing power in the Republic of Belarus became possible precisely due to this external backing.

In practice, the Republic of Belarus:

- does not possess an independent capacity to form and ensure its own security policy and protection of rights inside the country;
- lacks autonomous mechanisms for making and implementing strategic decisions outside the external coercive framework;
- is incapable of maintaining the existing power without systematic internal terror carried out by law enforcement and security bodies and other state coercive structures²⁴, as well as without direct and constant political, coercive and strategic support from the Putin regime.

Under these conditions, any attempts by international actors to compel the regime to comply with obligations inside the country inevitably go beyond human-rights or diplomatic pressure and acquire an interstate and military-political character. This excludes the possibility of sustainable external control over the implementation of guarantees and makes their real enforcement on the territory of the Republic of Belarus impossible.

²¹ Encyclopaedia Britannica, Operation Just Cause (U.S. invasion of Panama, capture and trial of Manuel Noriega), <https://www.britannica.com/event/Operation-Just-Cause>

²² Reuters, Venezuelan President Nicolás Maduro was captured by U.S. forces and taken to the United States to face federal charges (3 Jan 2026) <https://www.reuters.com/world/americas/loud-noises-heard-venezuela-capital-southern-area-without-electricity-2026-01-03/>

²³ Chatham House (Royal Institute of International Affairs). Transforming Belarus from a Russian asset to a buffer state for European security: How the West should engage with Minsk. London: Chatham House, 2026, (Summary). <https://www.chathamhouse.org/sites/default/files/2026-01/2026-01-14-transforming-belarus-russian-asset-buffer-state-european-security-astapenia.pdf>

²⁴ OSCE, United States Mission to the OSCE, On Human Rights Violations in Belarus, Statement delivered to the OSCE Permanent Council, Vienna, 19 November 2020, PC.DEL/1623/20, <https://www.osce.org/files/f/documents/3/a/472260.pdf>

As a result, the potential capacity for international pressure does not transform into a real capacity to protect released persons remaining on the territory of the Republic of Belarus.

10.5. The real limit of applicability of guarantees

Analysis of release practices shows that a legally formalized status of a released person acquires practical significance exclusively after departure from the territory of the Republic of Belarus.

Only outside the jurisdiction of the existing regime is it possible to:

- secure legal certainty of the released person's status;
- ensure physical and personal security;
- exclude repeated criminal or formally legal persecution;
- guarantee impossibility of a return to repressive measures under alternative formal grounds.

For persons remaining on the territory of the Republic of Belarus, the capacities of the international community are objectively limited²⁵. They allow observation, documentation, monitoring of individual cases and subsequent international legal assessment of events, but they are not capable of providing direct protection and do not prevent the application of repressive mechanisms.

Under these conditions, departure from the country becomes in practice the only way to realize any legal guarantees. This means that within the existing release model, expulsion is a mandatory element of the mechanism.

Without physical removal of a person from the regime's jurisdiction, any declared guarantees remain declarative and are not subject to real implementation. This limit of applicability of international guarantees determines the actual logic of what is occurring: protection of released persons is possible only outside the country, whereas inside the Republic of Belarus release without departure does not ensure termination of repressive impact and does not create conditions for real security.

10.6. Forced expulsion as a normalized form of repression

The absence of reaction to the case of Nikolai Statkevich, as well as to the subsequent wave of releases, led to consolidation of a practice in which forced expulsion came to be perceived as an acceptable and permissible outcome of release.

Within this acceptability, the following positions became established:

- release without restoration of civil and procedural rights became permissible and ceased to be regarded as a violation;
- departure from the country de facto became a mechanism of expelling a person from the territory of the state without termination of criminal or administrative prosecution;
- responsibility for the legal status, security and further fate of released persons was shifted onto external states and international structures;
- release procedures perform the function of legitimizing expulsion rather than restoring legal status.

Under these conditions, silence and lack of reaction on the part of international institutions cease to be a neutral position and in essence signify consent to the continuing repressive practice.

10.7. Concluding Findings

The analysis in this chapter is based on the situation in Belarus. It identifies a mechanism characteristic of authoritarian regimes, in which the subordination of courts and law-enforcement bodies to political power renders international guarantees unenforceable within the country.

The conducted analysis shows that the normative model for terminating the practice of forced expulsions retains its significance as a legal benchmark and evaluation criterion, but cannot be implemented inside the Republic of Belarus while the existing structure of power and control

²⁵ UN Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights, Belarus: Freeing political prisoners does not end policy of repression, warns UN expert, 17 December 2025.

<https://www.ohchr.org/en/press-releases/2025/12/belarus-freeing-political-prisoners-does-not-end-policy-repression-warns-un>

remains in place. This is due not to insufficient elaboration of mechanisms or absence of formal obligations, but to the absence of conditions for their execution.

The case of Nikolai Statkevich demonstrated this in practical terms. It showed that:

- any protective status established inside the country remains formal and unstable²⁶;
- refusal to leave is not regarded by the regime as a permissible scenario and entails repressive consequences²⁷;
- international actors do not possess instruments for actual protection of persons located on the territory of the state;
- real guarantees of security and legal certainty are possible exclusively outside the regime's jurisdiction.

Under these conditions, departure from the country turns not into a free choice, but into the only way to give release real substance. Attempts to ensure protection inside the country do not eliminate repressive risk, but merely reproduce the mechanism of forced expulsions, masking it as humanitarian or negotiation-based formats.

Consequently, forced expulsion within the established release practice is not a side effect or a consequence of procedural errors. It constitutes a necessary element of the functioning of the system, without which the declared guarantees remain declarative and unenforceable.

Ignoring this limit leads to normalization of a situation in which release without restoration of rights is considered acceptable, responsibility for the fate of released persons is effectively shifted onto external actors, and the practice of exile loses its status as a violation. As a result, a stable model of external repression is created, embedded in negotiation processes and devoid of corrective constraints.

Thus, any humanitarian or political initiatives that do not take into account the impossibility of real protection of released persons inside the Republic of Belarus do not terminate the practice of forced expulsions, but in fact support its preservation. Under these conditions, release ceases to mean termination of repression and is reduced to the relocation of a person beyond the country's borders. Recognition of this limit is necessary in order for release to once again be regarded as genuine termination of persecution, rather than its displacement outside the state.

²⁶ UN Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights, "Belarus: Freeing political prisoners does not end policy of repression, warns UN expert", 17 December 2025.
<https://www.ohchr.org/en/press-releases/2025/12/belarus-freeing-political-prisoners-does-not-end-policy-repression-warns-un>

²⁷ Associated Press, "Belarusian politician Mikola Statkevich returned to prison after refusing 'forced deportation'", 25 November 2025.
<https://apnews.com/article/53749ebbcd14ca9f286030404544c90d>

About the Author of the Report

Aleh Baradzin is the founder of the Foundation of Belarusian Political Prisoners in Poland, Chair of the Foundation Council, human rights defender and public figure. A former political prisoner of the Republic of Belarus.

Participates in the Foundation's activities at the level of strategic and institutional governance. Prior to repression in Belarus, he was the owner and head of two commercial companies.

In 2025, he completed professional training within the frameworks of programmes of UNITAR, ITC-ILO, UN DESA, UNEP, as well as joint initiatives of UNCTAD, UNHCR, IOM, the World Bank and the OSCE in the fields of politics, foundation governance and human rights activities.

In 1996, he was one of the founders and leaders of the Free Trade Union of Student Youth of the city of Gomel; since 2000, he has been a member of the Belarusian Helsinki Committee.

Appendices

Appendix A. Official response of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Belarus regarding the legal status of Mikola Statkevich

An official written reply issued by the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Belarus in response to an inquiry submitted by Mikola Statkevich's spouse.

The document states that Mikola Statkevich is serving a sentence pursuant to a court judgment and does not provide any information regarding his actual location or procedural status beyond a formal reference to the criminal sentence.

The response relies on domestic legislation on citizens' appeals and explicitly limits the scope of information provided.

Literal translation into English

MINISTRY OF INTERNAL AFFAIRS
OF THE REPUBLIC OF BELARUS
4 Garadski Val Street, Minsk, 220030
Tel./fax: (017) 218-79-62, 203-99-18
E-mail: uzgs@mvd.gov.by
21.11.2025 No. 55/4-37913

To:
Adamovich Maryna Mikhailovna

On the consideration of an application

The Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Belarus, within the scope of its competence, has considered your application.

We inform you that Statkevich M.V. is serving a sentence in accordance with the judgment of the Gomel Regional Court dated 14 December 2021.

On the basis of part six of Article 20 of the Law of the Republic of Belarus of 18 July 2011 No. 300-Z "On Appeals of Citizens and Legal Entities", the response sent to you may be appealed in court in the manner established by legislation.

Deputy Minister (signature)
G.A. Kazakevich

Original document (Belarusian/Russian)

**МІНІСТЭРСТВА
ЎНУТРАНЫХ СПРАЎ
РЭСПУБЛІКІ БЕЛАРУСЬ**

вул. Гарадскі Вал, 4, 220030, г. Мінск
тэл/факс (017) 218 79 62, 203 99 18
эл.пошта: uzgs@mvd.gov.by

21.11.2015 № 55/ч-3491эл
На № _____ ад _____

**МИНИСТЕРСТВО
ВНУТРЕННИХ ДЕЛ
РЕСПУБЛИКИ БЕЛАРУСЬ**

ул. Городской Вал, 4, 220030, г. Минск
тел/факс (017) 218 79 62, 203 99 18
эл.почта: uzgs@mvd.gov.by

Адамовіч Марыне Міхайлаўне
Вул. Гарадскі Вал, 4
220030, г. Мінск

Аб разглядзе заявы

У Міністэрстве ўнутраных спраў Рэспублікі Беларусь у рамках сваёй кампетэнцыі разгледжана Ваша заява.

Паведамляю, што Статкевіч М.В. адбывае пакаранне згодна з прыгаворам Гомельскага абласнога суда ад 14.12.2021.

На падставе часткі 6 артыкула 20 Закона Рэспублікі Беларусь ад 18 ліпеня 2011 г. № 300-З «Аб зваротах грамадзян і юрыдычных асобаў» сапраўдны адказ Вамі можа быць абскарджаны ў суд у парадку, устаноўленым заканадаўствам.

Намеснік Міністра

Г.А.Казакевіч

Appendix B. Notifications of the Belarusian State Appeals Portal and a Public Statement by the Spouse of N. V. Statkevich Regarding the Termination of Appeals Without a Substantive Response

This appendix contains:

- system notifications from the official Belarusian state appeals portal indicating that submitted appeals were left without a substantive review and without sending a response to the applicant;
- a public statement by Marina Adamovich, the spouse of political prisoner Nikolai Viktorovich Statkevich, describing the procedural handling of her appeals and the refusal of state bodies to provide information on his place of detention and legal status.

The materials document the practice of refusal by the state authorities of the Republic of Belarus to provide information on the place of detention and legal status of the convicted person, and demonstrate the formal and extra-procedural nature of the termination of correspondence.

Literal translation into English

Public statement by Marina Adamovich (8 October 2025)

“Yesterday late in the evening, in my personal account on the website obrashcheniya.by, the status of my appeal to Penal Colony No. 13 in Hlybokaye was updated (exactly seven days after the final deadline for a response). The status was changed from ‘In progress’ to ‘Left without a substantive response’.

For this refusal, the ‘authorized persons’ needed only 22 days instead of the legally established 15. And today, the same refusal appeared on the same website with regard to the Department for the Execution of Punishments as well. So, has the ‘instruction’ been received? As soon as it is reported with the well-known wording: ‘You are going to prison...’ - ‘I will go to prison...’ (c)?

Do we have some kind of secret places for serving a sentence, controlled by the Department for the Execution of Punishments and subordinate to no one (I emphasize the words ‘serving a sentence’ - this is not about a pre-trial detention center)?

Please refrain from comments that may cause trauma to people with a fragile mental constitution.”

System notifications from the state appeals portal.

Result of consideration of the appeal

Case reference number: No. 29-1-5

Without sending a response.

Result of consideration of the appeal

Left without substantive consideration:

Report on leaving the appeal without execution.

Original screenshots and photographic images of the documents are provided after this translation as part of Appendix B.

Результат рассмотрения обращения
Номер сформированного дела №29-1-5
Без направления ответа.

Результат рассмотрения обращения
Оставлено без рассмотрения по существу:
Рапорт об оставлении обращения без исполнения

Appendix C. Electronic record of an appeal submitted via the national appeals portal (obrascheniya.by) and notice of termination of correspondence

This document is an electronic record generated by the official Belarusian state portal for citizens' appeals (obrascheniya.by). It confirms the submission and registration of an appeal concerning the whereabouts of political prisoner Mikalai Viktaravich Statkevich.

The record further indicates that correspondence on this appeal was terminated, and that the response was sent by post without providing a scanned copy, thereby preventing access to the content of the reply through the electronic system.

Literal translation into English

“...In accordance with the reply of the Deputy Minister of Internal Affairs G.A. Kazakevich dated 21 November 2025 No. 35/A-379, my husband, Mikalai Viktaravich Statkevich, is serving a sentence in accordance with the judgment of the Gomel Regional Court dated 14 December 2021, by which he was sentenced to 14 years of imprisonment in a special-regime colony.

However, the indicated reply does not contain information about the specific institution of the penitentiary system of the Republic of Belarus where my husband is currently being held. I request to inform me where (in which correctional institution) M.V. Statkevich is currently located.”

Date of submission: 02 December 2025, 03:41

Date of registration: 02 December 2025

Result:

On termination of correspondence.

Response sent by post without scanning.

Original document (Belarusian)

18:01

VoLTE 4G+ 35%

< **Марына Адамовіч**

Все

Фото

Reels

Марына Адамовіч

8 окт. 2025 г. · 👥

Учора позна ўвечары ў асабістым кабінце на сайце абращения.бел абнавіўся статус майго звароту ў ПК-13 у Глыбокім (роўна праз сем дзён пасля крайняй даты на адказ). "На исполнении" змяніўся на "Оставлено без ответа по существу". Для гэтага адказу "ўпаўнаважаным асобам" спатрэбілася ўсяго толькі 22 дні супраць устаноўленых 15-ці. А ўжо сёння такі ж адказ на тым жа сайце з'явіўся і з ДВП.

То бок, "інструкцыя" атрыманая? Як толькі яна суадносіцца з вядомым выказваннем: "Ты ж в тюрму..." - "Пайду ў турму..."(с)?

Ці ў нас ёсць нейкія таемныя, не падначаленыя ДВП, месцы адбыцця пакарання (я падкрэсліваю слова "адбыцця", гэта не пра СІЗА)?

Калі ласка, устрымайцеся ад каментароў, якія могуць нанесці траўму асобам з тонкай душэўнай арганізацыяй. ((

Результат рассмотрения обраш
Номер сформированного дела №29

Без направления ответа.

Результат рассмотрения

лено без рассмотрения по существу:

